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On *The Virgin Suicides*: An Elegy to Entropy

The Virgin Suicides by Jeffrey Eugenides is a novel with a message which may at first seem elusive. We are left questioning why the Lisbon sisters end up killing themselves without fulfillment. It is likely that the author's intent is to make the reader question not only the deaths of the Lisbon sisters, but also the societal shortcomings that **pushed these girls past the complacency that plagues their community and into unrestrained existential despair. He reveals this intent in an elegy to entropy.** Eugenides writes his novel with the intent of exposing the reader to a perspective in which the progression of social, moral, communal, and individual deterioration are apparent. At the inception of the story the reader is immediately thrust into the environment of a pervasive dystopia through the memorable imagery of deterioration. The moral standards valued by the community in the book are utopian and inauthentic, exemplifying a declining society where simulations substitute for authenticity¹. The decline of men and boys demonstrated by the book is a further example of entropy. Eugenides presents all of this effectively in the form of an elegy.

Complex systems, societies being a prime example, have a tendency towards chaos and disorder, thus there is a tendency towards entropy. All non-societal organic systems follow the properties of Entropy. Entropy is not merely an occasionally observed phenomenon, but a codified physical property of the universe. The scientific definition of time itself is based on the order in which information tends towards disorder.² As with organic systems, thus human societies: the Roman Empire, the British Empire, now ours. Eugenides joins a list of great thinkers from centuries past in warning of the relentlessness of entropy.³ The Oxford English Dictionary defines the word elegy as “A song of lamentation, especially a funeral song or lament for the dead.” Renowned

¹ See *Simulacra and Simulation* by Jean Baudrillard

² Wikipedia contributors. "[Entropy \(arrow of time\)](#)." Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia.

³ [WordsDay: Entropy in literature](#)

Neuroscientist, Dr. Karl Friston, explains “The second law of thermodynamics tells us that the universe tends toward entropy, toward dissolution; but living things fiercely resist it.”⁴ The elegy in this story laments the passage of the girls and of the world. Eugenides describes the entropic nature of modern suburbia by utilizing stylistic devices characteristic of elegy.

Remembering is the key to elegy. The book is about remembering: Detroit falling apart, trees being cut down, the auto industry dying, “and the old men’s memories of how it used to be for them” but now “nevermore.”⁵ An elegy portrays the best as gone and mourns the memory’s distance from the present. Eugenides provides an elegiac description of the entropic decline of the community portrayed in the story. Eugenides' unique elegiac style subtly illustrates entropy successfully in an incredibly moving fashion. There are many stylistic devices used in the story that are an elegiac suggestion of entropy. One occurrence is the boys and Lisbon girls trading of sad songs over the phone, the songs themselves being elegies. The treehouse 'archive' and the reflection of the now middle aged men on their past and regretting the present as well as their numbered exhibits as an aid to remember what is lost.

The imagery of declining nature illustrates entropy. The imagery presented in the book shows deterioration. The imagery is a stylistic device; deterioration is entropy. There is a recurring theme of the Lisbon girls experiencing and witnessing death in their community. The girls’ concern for the increasing number of endangered species is one example. The author included these references intentionally. They are being killed by the ignorance of humanity. The book returns to the image of elm trees being removed by city workers because they are infected with “Dutch elm disease”. “It wasn't only the Lisbon house that changed but the street itself. The Parks Department continued to cut down trees, removing a sick elm to save the remaining twenty, then removing another to save the remaining nineteen, and so on and so on until only the half-tree remained in front of the Lisbons' old house.” Eugenides’ recurring reference of the image of this systematic removal is significant

⁴ ["The Genius Neuroscientist Who Might Hold the Key to True AI," WIRED](#)

⁵ [The Raven - Edgar Allan Poe](#)

as it symbolizes the community's destruction of itself. At one point the Lisbon sisters force themselves between the city workers and their beloved tree. This tree was clearly significant to them. More so than protecting Cecilia's attachment to it, the tree was symbolic of life, and perhaps of their lives. The girls ask why not let nature take its course? Workers say that the trees will all die if the diseased trees remain. The Lisbons then argue that the workers will remove all the trees anyway. Both the workers removing the trees and the natural disease killing the trees are symptoms of the natural inevitable decay that is entropy. "We got to see how truly unimaginative our suburb was, everything laid out on a grid whose bland uniformity the trees had hidden, and the old ruses of differentiated architectural styles lost their power to make us feel unique."(237) By the end, even the fish-flies die. Just like the trees, the people are breaking down just as does any complex system in this entropic community.

"Normally, people came out to say goodbye to their trees. It wasn't uncommon to see a family gathered on the lawn at a safe distance from the chain saws, a tired mom and dad with two or three long haired teenagers, and a poodle with a ribbon in its hair. People felt they owned the trees. Their dogs had marked them daily. Their children had used them for home plate. The trees had been there when they'd moved in, and had promised to be there when they moved out. But when the Parks Department came to cut them down, it was clear our trees were not ours but the city's, to do with as it wished."(173)

The description of declining community in *The Virgin Suicides* illustrates entropy. The first piece of evidence for this is the inauthentic moral standards exhibited by the members of the community, that are utopian and hypocritical. These standards are characteristic of entropic society. Eroding morality and humanity is a motif that runs in nearly all characters in the story. "She straightened the welcome mat with her toe, twice. Soon the paramedics ran out again, changed and electrified, and got the stretcher. A minute later they were carrying Therese out, facedown. Her dress, hiked up around her waist, revealed her unbecoming underwear, the color of an athletic bandage. The buttons in back had popped open to reveal a slice of mushroom-colored back.

Her hand kept falling Off the stretcher, though each time Mrs. Lisbon replaced it. "Stay," she commanded, to the hand apparently. But the hand flopped out again.”(213) The mother paradoxically values her religion and its beliefs over her own children when the religion teaches compassion. The story is filled with religious imagery and symbolism. The father doesn't know how to speak to his own daughters and takes comfort in speaking to the plants at school to console and relieve his internal repressed chaos. Another indication is when the minister sat down with the father. The father became emotional when the minister mentioned Cecilia but rejected his emotion and masked it by saying “double play.” Then there is the neighbors' lack of authentic empathy. Almost no one truly reached out to offer support. Letters of condolences were sent but most of them weren't even handwritten. Even those that were hand written were done out of custom rather than compassion. The other families only passed judgement on the Lisbon household and ‘reduced’ the tragedy into a commodity of casual small talk. “Knowing the rest of the city accepted the news as gospel only demoralized us further.” “Even our parents seemed to agree more and more with the television version of things, listening to the reporters' inanities as though they could tell us the truth about our own lives.”(220) Their views on their neighbors were manufactured by the media with their own eager consent, when they could have simply walked across the street and asked. One neighbor admitted to writing a letter to a local newspaper ridiculing the suicides “In a fit of righteous indignation under the hair dryer. She did not regret it. "You can't just stand by and let your neighborhood go down the toilet," she said. "We're good people around here.”(90) The people of the community intentionally and actively pursue the suppression of their humanity in a misguided effort toward communal welfare and fulfillment of communal values.

One particular example of this is the neighbors' infatuation with preserving an illusion of order by “raking [their lawns] in military ranks.” The author allocates a lot of page space into describing their lawn clearing practices. He clearly wants the reader to understand that these are the type of people who value conformity over their humanity. Eugenides throws in the image of a child following his his parents' footsteps

and their militaristic obsessiveness. He describes a family comprised of “ten people two parents, seven teenagers, the two-year-old Catholic mistake following with a toy rake.” The parents have every intention of preserving this practice for eternity, passed down from generation to generation. What is so eerie is that the suburban families enjoy this. The intensity with which they partake in this compulsive practice is also disturbing. Eugenides describes the passion of their insistent raking as “so keen we raked up the grass itself, leaving patches of dirt.” and that the “pleasure [they] felt all the way to [their] bowels.” Their obsessive orthodoxy is a testament to the community’s fabrication. This suburban community’s behavior is a testament to societal entropy. It is ironic when one neighbor says Cecilia just wanted out of the house when she really wanted out of that community. The sisters would get magazines detailing life in far away places far away from their suburban nightmare its its values.

‘White Flight’ is another example. Eugenides briefly presents the imagery of black maids standing on street corners. The suburb is a result of white flight. The community was founded with the intention of maintaining an impossible and destructive utopian society where there is conformity and sameness. Diversity is a dirty desire in their view. Its an unreachable goal. The definition of utopian is literally unattainable. When they try to reach it is inherent that there will be conflict. Furthermore, the white-washed world they desire is inauthentic and harmful because diversity allows for differing viewpoints that can delay the development of entropy.

Lisbon girls look on in horror as people grow old and die without ever having meaning in their life. They are robotic. They live because they are told to do so.

The author wants the readers to be confronted with the ugliness his characters avoid. They are immersed in the suburbs where normalcy and purity are fetishized. It shuts out the darkness that is such a necessary component of humanity. The experience of death and suffering is crucial to the human experience. They are trying to disconnect from what is there. The media’s portrayals of complex issues are dumbed down and

inhuman. All the neighbors watch the news and believe it. It is true that incredible people have come from suburbia. Eugenides 'suburbia may not lead to the end of civilization, but it embraces the stagnation of the development of the human spirit. What is it exactly that it extinguishes? External weakness is not acceptable. The characters push humanity down deep within themselves. There is no authentic mutual support within the community, rather, the community is a mere simulacrum.⁶

The community is annoyed with the Lisbons' lack of conformity, but striving for conformity, Mrs. Lisbon puts a beige dress on Cecilia that she hated. "She was dressed not in the wedding gown, which Mrs. Lisbon had thrown away, but in a beige dress with a lace collar, a Christmas gift from her grandmother which she had refused to wear in life." (36) She didn't have a choice. The mother is obsessed with fitting into suburbia and wants her to appear as normal. She is overly concerned with Cecilia biting her nails. They treat Cecilia like a pet when she is living and when she is dead.⁷

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The decline of men and boys is emblematic of entropy. The boys are plagued by inaction and immaturity. They are effete, ineffective, lacking courage, lacking life energy, and are trapped by inauthentic consciousness. "The essence Of the suicides consisted not of sadness or mystery but simple selfishness. The girls took into their own hands decisions better left to God. They became too powerful to live among us, too self-concerned, too visionary, too blind." (242) The boys are speaking as if their own rights have been violated and that it is they who had experienced the greatest loss. Seeing girls as objects precludes an actual relationship as one does not have a relationship with an object. The result of this is the production up of stunted individuals. These boys are emotionally stunted. There is no depth to their thoughts and emotions. "Inside their house they were prisoners; outside, lepers. And so they hid from the world, waiting for someone—for us—to save

⁶ Simulacra and Simulation is a 1981 philosophical treatise by Jean Baudrillard

⁷ Warm bath of complacency and late stage capitalist consumerism. While everything is dying and deteriorating due to entropy everyone is "happy."

them.”(193) This illustrates the boys conception that they must be the girls “nights in shining armor” because of their obsessiveness over their fantasies. It's all in their imagination. Its like they are play acting. Despite their utter inaction, they imagine a narrative of themselves being protagonists of a love story that is absolutely not grounded in reality. Near the end of the story the boys share their collective dream in which they fulfill the courageous role that they have painted of themselves. “The knowledge welled in us that we would soon be in the car with the girls, driving them out of our green neighborhood and into the pure, free desolation of back roads we didn't even know yet.” “Unknown roads took shape in our minds. We saw ourselves cutting swaths through cattails, freshwater inlets, old boatyards. At some gas station we would ask for the ladies' room key because the girls would be too shy. We would play the radio with the windows open.”(207) The boys never go deep. The boy under the bleachers promises he'll call one of the sisters. He thinks he is really in love, yet he never calls her. Boys don't have the tools for depth. It's never taught to them. Their community actively tries to extinguish and reject it. The boys aren't allowed to become men. The boys are really material and shallow. The boys and this mindset in particular is a representation of their whole community. All suburbans have a tendency toward inaction. The big picture is trying to point at what's wrong with a group of people trying to pick themselves and remove themselves from society, losing their humanity. The collective narrators are pathetic products of suburbia. They were unable to prevent the destruction of the most meaningful things in their lives. They are dust in the face of entropy.⁸

Perhaps the girls killed themselves when realizing the inevitability of impermanence in their community. This book is a lesson; we must learn from it. This book teaches us a lesson that is vital to meaningful living for all of us. The characters in the book exhibit the same symptoms of what we experience. The story dramatizes and exaggerates the circumstances to try to make a larger impact on us. The girls **thought** they had nothing meaningful to live for. If they thought that their lives were important and had potential to do good, they probably would not have ended their lives. Suicide is motivated by some deep, dark despair that alters the mind's

⁸ [Janey Tracey, In Defense of the Unsatisfying Ending: *The Virgin Suicides*, Emerson College](#)

chemistry so significantly it causes suicidal intent. We end up wondering why the girls kill themselves. Why would the author not give a reason or explain the deeper meaning? It is because this is for the reader to explore. Why write this except for our enlightenment? We learn of impermanence, which is the recognition and embrace of the reality of entropy. This is one of man's greatest fears: the inevitable inherent unknowableness of death. Thus religion is created with billions and billions of believers, such as Mrs. Lisbon, who are drawn by the bare suggestion that there could be an eternity. Many will be left asking what can be taken from this. Why go on?⁹ There is a boundary between the conservative purity of sprawling suburbia and the raw emotional, carnal, and visceral humanity that is expressed with suicide. Impermanence is beautiful, in a similar way to the image of Cecilia impaled on the fence is beautiful, like the beautiful images of Saint Sebastian, pierced by arrows.¹⁰ The Ascetics of the buddhist practice have been aware of impermanence for millenia embracing it with meditation, just as Eugenides embraces it with this elegy. Perhaps the Lisbon girls' reason for ending their lives is their realization and acceptance of the inevitable deterioration. After all, Entropy is destined to rule our future. The book's lack of explicit explanation for the suicides may not be satisfying but ultimately that was not the point of the book, rather the suicides fit into the bigger picture - a written memory of loss - an elegy to entropy.¹¹

⁹ **It may be dangerous to make despair only an intellectual exercise.** Nothing real has changed after attaining this awareness. The only thing that has shifted is your perspective.

¹⁰ [Saint Sebastian - pierced by arrows on account of his faith](#)

¹¹ Although this may not be the author's intent, it is simply what I took from it. It is an important message all the same that was, in some form, inspired by the book.